

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

Deliverable 2.2

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Abbreviations List

API	Application Programming Interface
CRIS	Current Research Information System
DC	Dublin Core
DCMI Metadata Terms	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative Metadata Terms (often mentioned as dcterms by the commonly used namespace)
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUPL	European Public License
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FOSS	Free Open-Source Software
IF	Interoperability Framework
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON for Linked Data
maDMP	Machine Actionable Data Management Plan
OAI	Open Archives Initiative
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OID	Object Identifier
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
PMH	Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

URN	Uniform Resource Name
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This report accompanies D2.2 “OSTrails Software and Services V1” which refers to the first release of the software produced by WP2 as a result of alignment with the objectives of the project and the expectations, directives and requirements stemming from work of WP1 and WP2 and the Description of Work of the project.

The report presents the basis upon which work is performed, which originates from (a) the OSTrails Interoperability Framework requirements, (b) the alignment with indicated common technologies and standards, (c) the filling of the gaps identified in technologies at hand during previous period and (d) the targets set in the Description of Work of OSTrails.

The software addressed by D2.2 work predates OSTrails project and is organised in four categories: (a) DMP Platforms, (b) SKG Platforms, (c) FAIR Assessment Platforms and (d) Other Supporting Services and Platforms, as established in work preceding D2.2 delivery.

This report presents a self-contained comprehensive listing of this software, its status and how to access it - as a service, source code, documentation, executable or in any other form foreseen for each platform - a summary of the work performed in the preceding period to align with OSTrails requirements. Each software platform also reports forthcoming work in OSTrails to further align with the requirements.

In total 34 tools are listed in the aforementioned manner, out of which 3 DMP tools, 10 SKG Platforms, 8 FAIR Assessment Platforms and 13 supporting services and platforms. Out of those, approximately 75% has already implemented some alignment in OSTrails, the other 25% plans to implement refinements in the remaining two WP2 formal software releases. Most of those tools are Free and Open-Source Platforms.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

This deliverable is product of work performed in Work Package 2, “Plan-Track-Assess Alignment Implementation”, of OSTrails project, across all of its 4 tasks, that is Data Management Plan (DMP) Platforms (T2.1), Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) Platforms (T2.2), FAIR² Assessment Platforms (T2.3) and Supporting Services and Resources (T2.4) alignment.

This is the first of 3 versions of the deliverable that will be presented, with increasing alignment of the software, the next two are planned for M24 and M32 of the project.

1.2. Deliverable Description

This report presents D2.2 which contains the first release of the software produced by Work Package 2 tasks which target the alignment of existing software platforms and tools with the objectives of the project as presented into its Description of Work and the expectations, directives and requirements emanating from work carried out so far by both Work Package 1 and Work Package 2. These fall into the following categories:

- Requirements coming from Interoperability framework
- Expectations for adoption of core technologies and standards identified as suitable and proven for adoption across tools.
- Directives for gaps that need to be filled in.
- Specific work targets introduced at Description of Work.

The software dealt with in WP2 is organised in four categories:

- (a) DMP Platforms,
- (b) SKG Platforms,
- (c) FAIR Assessment Platforms and
- (d) Other Supporting Services and Platforms

Those have been established in work preceding D2.2 delivery and presented in D2.1 entitled “.1: Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance”.

As the software predates OSTrails project, the deliverable refers to enhancements and extensions of existing software, rather than new platforms and tools. However not all software analysed in the context of WP2 and presented in D2.1 will be evolving in WP2, thus specific platforms / tools are not included in this report.

² FAIR refers to principles for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets emphasizing on machine-actionability allowing researchers, scientists, and other human stakeholders to deal with data of rapidly increasing volume, complexity, and creation speed.

Although this report focuses on software that is evolving in WP2, selected platforms that have plans for evolving in WP2 are also listed in this report, however no specific developments are being presented yet. Those developments will be presented in the updates of the report that will accompany future software releases, as per Description of Work.

As mentioned, this report accompanies software delivery as a supporting document and is not itself the deliverable per se. It aims to provide the reader with a self-contained, comprehensive summary of the work performed up to this software release and shape the direction of forthcoming work, a schema for the homogeneous description of the software implemented has been shaped and utilised across the document.

Following this approach, the main part of this report consists of information provided for each software component that has evolved in this period, along the lines presented earlier, referring to:

- Identification of the software, containing the formal name of the service / platform / tool, the category the software falls into, and its Technology Readiness Level, along any identifier or version number applicable to it.
- References for accessing the platform/service and/or its source code, if Open Source, and its documentation along with any relevant information about how it is being offered to its users/audience.
- Licensing and ownership information.
- Reference to software Quality Assurance measures taken in delivery of the software.
- Brief presentation of the work is performed in OSTrails up to M14, in alignment with its objectives.
- Plan for the work to be performed in alignment with the main project's milestones.

1.3. Structure of Document

The rest of the document is structured as follows.

- In section 2, the requirements motivating the implementation of the software are presented, organised in different groups depending on their origin and form.
- In section 3 the work performed in each software component, that falls under the category of "DMP platform" is presented.
- In section 4 and under a similar fashion with the previous section, the SKG Platforms work performed is presented.
- In section 5, in a similar way the FAIR Assessment Platforms are listed.
- In section 6, work on all remaining software supporting the three aforementioned categories of platforms, is presented.
- Finally, in section 7, overall conclusions on the progress of work and key points of next steps of implementation are presented.

2. Requirements

In the following paragraphs the requirements behind the work performed on OSTrails Software and Services.

2.1. OSTrails IF requirements

Requirements established in OSTrails Deliverable D2.1" Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework tools compliance" [1] are listed in **Table 1** .

Table 1: DMP, SKG, FAIR assessment and general interoperability requirements for OSTrails software

REQUIREMENT ID	REQUIREMENT DESCRIPTION
DMP-R1	DMP IF (Interoperability Framework) <i>must</i> use RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-Actionable DMPs (maDMPs).
DMP-R2	DMP IF <i>must</i> provide comprehensive, versioned documentation for Application Programming Interface (API) adopters. It <i>should</i> include basic principles, conventions, and examples to facilitate integration and ensure interoperability.
DMP-R3	DMP IF <i>should</i> develop an RDA DMP Common Standard extension with respect to existing ontologies and vocabularies such as Schema.org, Dublin Core Metadata Initiative Terms (DCMI Metadata Terms aka DC Terms), or Data Cite.
DMP-R4	DMP IF <i>must</i> specify API(s) using OpenAPI following Representational State Transfer (REST) architectural style. Such API(s) <i>should</i> use JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) as (one of) the supported file formats for communication and data exchange.
DMP-R5	DMP IF <i>may</i> propose representation and exchange of DMPs in Resource Description Framework (RDF) or other semantically rich formats (while in alignment with Research Data Alliance (RDA) DMP Common Standard). In this sense, DMP IF <i>could</i> align data schemas with external ontologies and vocabularies, such as Schema.org, DC Terms, and Data Cite, to enhance interoperability and support standardised data sharing practices across different platforms.
DMP-R6	DMP IF <i>may</i> propose notification mechanism (from/to DMP Platforms) based on existing World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) recommendations (Web Notifications, Linked Data Notifications).
DMP-R7	DMP IF <i>may</i> facilitate deeper integration with institutional systems like Current Research Information System (CRIS) by specifying APIs and data models that are compatible with these environments. This <i>could</i> include predefined endpoints for data exchange and alignment with institutional workflows.
DMP-R8	DMP IF <i>should</i> establish a compliance verification process or badging system to ensure that tools adhere to the OpenAPI specification and the RDA DMP Common Standard.

SKG-R1	SKG IF <i>must</i> support common data formats and standards such as JSON, Extensible Markup Language (XML), and JSON for Linking Data (JSON-LD) to ensure interoperability and data integration across various SKGs following the RDA SKG IF specification (and eventually extend it or contribute to it).
SKG-R2	SKG IF <i>should</i> design robust API(s) (e.g., REST, SPARQL) and API documentation using OpenAPI/Swagger UI, allowing external services to query, retrieve, and ingest data. This will enhance integration with other scientific tools and platforms.
SKG-R3	SKG IF <i>must</i> align with Persistent Identifier (PID) systems such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID), and Research Organization Registry (ROR) for improved data traceability, attribution, and reliability across SKGs.
SKG-R4	SKG IF <i>may</i> facilitate crosswalks between different data models used by various SKGs, ensuring compatibility and integration even when custom models are used. This could include mappings between internal and external schemas like Dublin Core or DataCite.
SKG-R5	SKG IF <i>should</i> specify a common secure authentication and authorisation mechanisms such as OAuth 2.0/OpenID Connect for managing access to data, particularly for sensitive operations like modifying or contributing records (i.e. for cases where open access is not possible).
SKG-R6	SKG IF <i>should</i> specify standards for metadata harvesting using protocols like Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH), enabling SKGs to easily aggregate and share metadata across different repositories, improving data accessibility and discoverability.
SKG-R7	SKG IF <i>may</i> enable event notifications for external services, allowing them to subscribe to changes or updates in SKG records through APIs. This will ensure timely updates and interactions between SKGs and external services.
SKG-R8	SKG IF <i>should</i> support validation and schema compliance mechanisms to ensure high data quality and alignment with international standards such as ones indicated by European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Working Groups, enhancing the reliability and consistency of scientific data across platforms.
FAIR-R1	FAIR IF <i>must</i> specify standardised API endpoints (e.g., OpenAPI) for exposing metadata related to FAIR assessments and initiating tests or algorithms.
FAIR-R2	FAIR IF <i>should</i> bring a data model for exchanging test specifications, test results, metrics, and benchmarks including related metadata.

FAIR-R3	FAIR IF <i>should</i> establish a governance framework to ensure consistency and quality in tests, test implementations, and metrics across various FAIR assessment tools.
FAIR-R4	FAIR IF <i>should</i> ensure that tools aggregate and report results in a standardised format (e.g., JSON-LD), allowing seamless integration of outputs from different assessments.
FAIR-R5	FAIR IF <i>may</i> promote interoperability by adopting common schemas and formats (e.g., JSON or RDF formats), enhancing data compatibility and exchange between diverse tools.
FAIR-R6	FAIR IF <i>should</i> allow to verify compliance with its specifications to ensure that assessment tools and services align.
IF-R1	The OSTrails IF <i>must</i> use existing established data models and specifications such as RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs or SKG-IF (eventually contribute to them or extend them, based on specific needs).
IF-R2	The OSTrails IF <i>must</i> provide comprehensive, versioned documentation for adopters, including principles, conventions, and examples.
IF-R3	The OSTrails IF <i>should</i> support common data formats and standards such as JSON, XML, JSON-LD, and RDF to ensure interoperability and data integration.
IF-R4	The OSTrails IF <i>should</i> specify a common way for secure authentication and authorisation mechanisms, such as OAuth 2.0 or OpenID Connect.
IF-R5	The OSTrails IF <i>must</i> align with persistent identifier systems (e.g., DOI, ORCID, ROR) for improved data traceability and reliability.
IF-R6	The OSTrails IF <i>should</i> establish a compliance verification process to ensure adherence for adopting tools.
IF-R7	The OSTrails IF <i>should</i> use existing widely used ontologies and vocabularies (e.g., Schema.org, DCTerms, DataCite) to enhance data interoperability.
IF-R8	The OSTrails IF <i>should</i> design APIs following OpenAPI specifications and REST architectural styles, with JSON as a supported format for data exchange.
IF-R9	The OSTrails IF <i>should</i> provide mechanisms for validation and schema compliance to ensure high data quality and adherence to international standards.
IF-R10	The framework <i>may</i> propose the representation and exchange of data in semantically rich formats like RDF to enhance interoperability.
IF-R11	The framework <i>may</i> facilitate deeper integration with institutional systems (e.g., CRIS) by specifying compatible APIs and data models.
IF-R12	The framework <i>may</i> enable event notifications for external services to subscribe to changes or updates in records.

IF-R13	The framework <i>must</i> allow for future extensions and contributions to accommodate emerging technologies and practices.
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2.2. Indicated common technologies and standards

Here are the core technologies and standards identified as suitable and proven for alignment across the mentioned tools:

Table 2: Common technologies and standards for OSTrails software

COMMON TECHNOLOGY / STANDARD	DESCRIPTION
DMP Common Standard	For the creation and management of Data Management Plans (DMPs), adopting the DMP Common Standard ensures consistency and interoperability across different DMP platforms.
Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) IF	Implementing the SKG Interchange Format promotes a unified approach to data representation and integration within science knowledge graphs.
REST APIs with OpenAPI	Utilising REST APIs documented and specified with OpenAPI ensures consistent and accessible data exchange and integration across systems.
OAI-PMH Metadata Harvesting for	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) is crucial for effective metadata sharing, synchronisation, and aggregation between repositories and consumers/clients.
Persistent Identifiers	Employing persistent identifiers such as DOI, Uniform Resource Name (URN), and Handle supports reliable referencing and long-term access to research outputs, concepts, and actors in the research ecosystem
Controlled Vocabularies and Taxonomies	Using standardised vocabularies and taxonomies ensures consistent classification and description of research data, enhancing discoverability and interoperability. Common vocabularies can be then used for various use cases, e.g., defining test results in terms of FAIR assessment, or supporting the DMP Common Standard and its extension.

2.3. Gaps identified

While confronting the information about tools with OSTrails Pathways and Interoperability Framework (IF), we identified the following gaps that need to be filled in.

Table 3: Identified gaps for OSTrails software

GAP	DESCRIPTION
Notifications	Current tools often lack comprehensive notification systems to alert users about updates, changes, or issues related to data or metadata. There are various options and standards to follow when designing an interoperable solution such as notifications according to the W3C recommendations (Web Notifications ³ and Linked Data Notifications ⁴).
Provenance Documentation	While some tools use provenance models (e.g. through PROV-O), there is variability in the implementation of standards for documenting the history and context of data processes (in SKGs, DMPs as well as some FAIR assessment tools and other supporting tools).
Integration with Emerging Standards	As new standards and technologies emerge, there is a need for ongoing alignment and updates to ensure compatibility and relevance. In other words, the tools as well as specifications for interoperability needs to adopt mechanism for evolution over time.
Semantic Data Representation	While tools tend to adopt existing vocabularies and ontologies where suitable for semantic and interoperable representation (e.g. as JSON-LD in addition to custom JSON representation), more extensive use of RDF technologies is rather missing. Linking external resources, (FAIR) Signposting, or SPARQL endpoints are very rare among the analysed tools. Still, adopting at least JSON-LD RDF representation is a reasonable first step.

³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/notifications/>

⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/ldn/>

2.4. Description of Work targets

Specific targets have been identified upon OSTrails definition⁵ for Supporting Services and Platforms, as presented in **Table 4**.

Table 4: Supporting Services and Platforms work targets

TOOL/SERVICE	TARGET
FAIRsharing	Enrich SKGs with the clusters; align to API specs; upgrade to provide content for DMP authoring and FAIR assessment; serve as registry of FAIR metrics tests.
OpenOrgs	Align to new set of APIs to share organisation information. Improve syncing to ROR and other organisation databases.
OpenAIRE Broker	Extend to new types of digital objects. Possibly extend notification system to send and receive standardised messages related to requests and responses for peer review and endorsement of resources in repositories via W3C standards Linked Data Notifications and Activity Streams 2.0, using libraries of The COAR Notify Project .
CESSDA ELST	Improve metadata annotation of multiple digital objects and link to other SKGs/DMPs.
SSH Vocabulary Commons	Extend APIs to make it visible/aligned with the SSH SKGs/DMPs.
ROHub	Align APIs to provide a single-entry point to all ROHub resources and associated metadata as contextualised subgraphs of an SKG and connect them so that they are findable in EOSC explore.
Lenticular Lens	Extend to interact with the SKGs and the supporting vocabularies to create and validate alignments between them.
SSH Data Citation Service	Align with new APIs to make its content available for inclusion in SSH domain SKGs.
SOMEF	Align APIs with extended metadata descriptions of software records based on their documentation, code and files.

⁵ Table 5 - Supporting tools and services in OSTrails, OSTrails Grant Agreement.

3. DMP Platforms

Here we describe DMP platforms software / services

3.1. Argos/OpenCDMP

Name	Argos (Service) / OpenCDMP (Software)		
Category	DMP		
Service URL	https://argos.openaire.eu/		
Version	1.0	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	CITE, OpenAIRE	Contributors	ARC
License	Code: EUPL1.2 (https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/licence/european-union-public-licence-version-12-eupl) Documentation: CC By 4.0 (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)		
Forms of availability	Source code and Docker Container Images		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/OpenCDMP/OpenCDMP		
Documentation URL	https://argos.openaire.eu/user-guide		
Other repositories	Source code: https://github.com/OpenCDMP/OpenCDMP Container Images: https://hub.docker.com/u/opencdmp Maven: https://mvnrepository.com/artifact/org.opencdmp		
PID	Not available		
Software Quality Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CI/CD infrastructure to ensure repeatable, trusted delivery. - Static Code Analysis using SonarQube software. - OWASP Top 10 compliance. - Use of industry standard AuthN/AuthZ solutions and practices. 		

<p>Work performed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alignment to IF early developments: Early API evolution to address IF expectations for DMP read/write operations, replacement of security infrastructure adopting KeyCloak as platform’s AuthN/AuthZ provider, implementation of pluggability mechanisms, early work on notifications (design). - Enhancement of data model to accommodate upcoming FAIRness and evaluation results, support of multiple persistent identifiers. - maDMP implementation improvement. Several minor improvements and implementation of maDMP support in blueprints. - Alignment with pilots’ early requirements to capture the significantly varying needs of various communities. Community isolation, visual adaptation and behavior. Security, interoperability configuration, pluggability etc. - Early work on isolation of “commons” software components. - Update of documentation to cover all changes and gradual improvements to align with project’s directives with the project. 								
<p>Milestones</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="448 1012 646 1055">Month</th> <th data-bbox="646 1012 1374 1055">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1055 646 1218"> <p>18</p> </td> <td data-bbox="646 1055 1374 1218"> <p>Finalisation of data model to capture DMP FAIR assessment and Evaluation requirements. First release of IF aligned API. High priority pilot’s requirements fulfilment.</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1218 646 1458"> <p>24</p> </td> <td data-bbox="646 1218 1374 1458"> <p>Full support of pilot’s requirements. Implementation of IF aligned API and architecture. Integration with FAIR assessment and evaluation tools. Continue working on other previously delivered features.</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1458 646 1856"> <p>32</p> </td> <td data-bbox="646 1458 1374 1856"> <p>Addressing of additional pilot’s requirements based on prioritisation of requests. Notification protocol support. Broadening of IF aligned API and architecture. Delivery of commons/ Final shaping of documentation according to project’s requirements. Continue working on other previously delivered features and new technical directions pointed out by the project.</p> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	<p>18</p>	<p>Finalisation of data model to capture DMP FAIR assessment and Evaluation requirements. First release of IF aligned API. High priority pilot’s requirements fulfilment.</p>	<p>24</p>	<p>Full support of pilot’s requirements. Implementation of IF aligned API and architecture. Integration with FAIR assessment and evaluation tools. Continue working on other previously delivered features.</p>	<p>32</p>	<p>Addressing of additional pilot’s requirements based on prioritisation of requests. Notification protocol support. Broadening of IF aligned API and architecture. Delivery of commons/ Final shaping of documentation according to project’s requirements. Continue working on other previously delivered features and new technical directions pointed out by the project.</p>
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3.2. DAMAP

Name	DAMAP, A tool for machine actionable DMPs		
Category	DMP		
Service URL	https://damap.it.tuwien.ac.at/		
Version	V 4.3.0	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	Technische Universität Wien / Technische Universität Graz	Contributors	Technische Universität Wien Technische Universität Graz
License	MIT License (https://opensource.org/license/mit)		
Forms of availability	Code repository		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/tuwien-csd/damap-frontend https://github.com/tuwien-csd/damap-backend		
Documentation URL	https://damap.org/		
Other repositories	None		
PID	Not Available		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Unit Tests Static Code Analysis using SonarQube software.		
Work performed	Alignment with the RDA DMP Common standard for machine actionable DMPs. The Invenio-DAMAP integration connects InvenioRDM-based data repositories with DAMAP-based data management plan (DMP)		

	tools. (Currently, this connection is one-way, from InvenioRDM to the DMPs.) This connection automatically prefills information in the DMPs by drawing details from the repository such as dataset size, storage, and license information. The integration uses maDMPs, based on the RDA DMP Common Standard, to drive this process and reduce manual data entry, minimize errors, and ensure that datasets mentioned in DMPs are correctly linked to their corresponding records in the repository.								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Align with RDA DMP Common standard and adopt the new changes in the recommendation</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Adopt maDMP API</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Integrate with DMP Evaluation Service</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Align with RDA DMP Common standard and adopt the new changes in the recommendation	24	Adopt maDMP API	32	Integrate with DMP Evaluation Service
Month	Description								
18	Align with RDA DMP Common standard and adopt the new changes in the recommendation								
24	Adopt maDMP API								
32	Integrate with DMP Evaluation Service								

3.3. Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW)

Name	FAIR Wizard (Service) / Data Stewardship Wizard (Software)		
Category	DMP		
Service URL	https://fair-wizard.com/ , https://ds-wizard.org		
Version	4.14	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	Codevence	Contributors	
License	Apache License 2.0 http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0		
Forms of availability	Source code and Docker Container Images, SaaS		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/ds-wizard https://github.com/ds-wizard/engine-frontend https://github.com/ds-wizard/engine-backend		

	https://github.com/ds-wizard/engine-tools				
Documentation URL	https://guide.ds-wizard.org/en/latest/				
Other repositories	https://github.com/ds-wizard/dsw-deployment-example				
PID	Not available				
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Developing with industry best practices (https://www.bestpractices.dev/en/projects/4975)</p> <p>CI/CD Infrastructure</p> <p>E2E tests, unit test frontend and backend</p> <p>QA process</p>				
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued development of Knowledge Models maDMP workflows, focusing on standardization and user interface improvements to meet RDA DMP Common Standard requirements. Refined knowledge management structures for compatibility with IF specifications and RDA DMP Common Standard. Developed preliminary API adapter prototypes to support interoperability with IF ecosystem while keeping the internal data structures and flexibility. Aligned feature priorities based on gathered use case requirements from pilot projects, ensuring responsiveness to diverse community needs. Preliminary design for inclusion of DMP evaluation services following the current specification from T3.3 				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>API adapter compliant with the current DMP API specification with flexibility through KM entity annotations for mappings. Enhanced alignment with DMP Common Standards. Designs and changes based on requirements from relevant pilots. Preliminary integrations and integration enhancements with specific services (e.g. FAIRsharing).</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	API adapter compliant with the current DMP API specification with flexibility through KM entity annotations for mappings. Enhanced alignment with DMP Common Standards. Designs and changes based on requirements from relevant pilots. Preliminary integrations and integration enhancements with specific services (e.g. FAIRsharing).
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18	API adapter compliant with the current DMP API specification with flexibility through KM entity annotations for mappings. Enhanced alignment with DMP Common Standards. Designs and changes based on requirements from relevant pilots. Preliminary integrations and integration enhancements with specific services (e.g. FAIRsharing).				

	24	Updated API adapter for maDMPs. Preliminary DMP Evaluation service integration. Adoption of current OSTrails AP for maDMPs.
	32	Integration of DMP Evaluation service integration, integration with FAIR evaluation services and other services as identified as need in pilots. Updated API adapter and mappings according to latest OSTrails AP.

4. SKG Platforms

4.1. CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC)

Name	CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) - ID002		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/		
Version	3.7.0	TRL	8 ⁶
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers, DoraVentures, Fox Online Solutions, Open Concept
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0 Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint, app marketplace		
Code repository URL	Application: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.searchkit.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.metadata.harvester.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.userguide.git OAI-PMH endpoint (SKG API): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.doc-store.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.client.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.oai-pmh-repo-handler.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.oai-pmh-repo-handler.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.devguide.git 		

⁶ <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

Documentation URL	<p>User Guide: https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/documentation/</p> <p>Search API: https://api.tech.CESSDA.eu/ (select 'CESSDA DC Search API v2')</p> <p>OAI-PMH API: https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=Identify</p> <p>OAI-PMH Developer's guide: https://CESSDA-metadata-aggregator.readthedocs.io/en/stable/</p>
Other repositories	<p>Zenodo (Application):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786299 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786355 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5711127 <p>Zenodo (OAI-PMH endpoint):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779957 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779936 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779782 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779897 <p>EOSC EU Node Marketplace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/datasources/21.11166%252Fu6za4c <p>SSH Open Marketplace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/etR4oA
PID	<p>Application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 10.5281/zenodo.3786299 - 10.5281/zenodo.3786355 - 10.5281/zenodo.5711127 <p>OAI-PMH endpoint:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 10.5281/zenodo.5779957 - 10.5281/zenodo.5779936 - 10.5281/zenodo.5779782 - 10.5281/zenodo.5779897
Software Quality	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.CESSDA.eu/sml/index.html). Examples:</p>

Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md <p>The Jenkins build breaks if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/software/quality-gate.html)</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and README files badged accordingly. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md <p>Tooling</p> <p>Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis)</p> <p>SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability)</p> <p>JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)</p>								
Work performed	Mapping between CESSDA data catalogue metadata and RDA SKG IF model.								
Milestones	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr style="background-color: #d3d3d3;"> <th style="text-align: left;">Month</th> <th style="text-align: left;">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">18</td> <td>Incorporate more persistent identifiers such as ORCID and ROR.</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">24</td> <td>First implementation of SKG-IF compliant API.</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">32</td> <td>Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Incorporate more persistent identifiers such as ORCID and ROR.	24	First implementation of SKG-IF compliant API.	32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
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32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.								

4.2. FAIRsharing

Name	FAIRsharing
Category	SKG
Service URL	https://fairsharing.org , https://api.fairsharing.org

Version	N/A	TRL	8 ⁷
Copyright owner(s)	University of Oxford	Contributors	Several ⁸
License	Content: CC-BY-SA-4.0, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/legalcode		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint, data catalogue		
Code repository URL	<p>Web application: https://github.com/FAIRsharing/fairsharing.github.io/</p> <p>There's also a private API repository.</p>		
Documentation URL	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing		
Other repositories	https://github.com/FAIRsharing/FAIRsharing-Assistant		
PID	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2abjs5		
Software Quality Assurance measures	CI unit testing, code coverage measurement, njsscan, codacy scanning, brakeman testing on API, API integration testing.		
Work performed	<p>Contributed to the SKG-IF architecture and enriched the FAIRsharing content and graph by working with clusters' champions, to meet their needs as well as the requirements of the DMPs and the FAIR tools. Integration with DSW is completed, while it is partial with Argos and planned with DAMAP.</p> <p>Contributed to the definition of the FAIR assessment IF of Dimensions, Metrics, Benchmarks and Tests. Designed and implemented the new FAIRassist registry component of FAIRsharing, to assist with the assessment. This new registry and (and knowledge graph) will describe FAIR Principles (or Dimensions), related Metrics and Benchmarks (that will be related to relevant</p>		

⁷ <https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSC/Service+Maturity+Classification>

⁸ https://fairsharing.org/community_champions/our_champions

	standards, in the main FAIRsharing registry), the latter two cross-referenced to the Tests.								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Users, DMP and FAIR tools requirement gathering</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Testing and piloting SKG-IF and FAIR-IF</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Production system</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Users, DMP and FAIR tools requirement gathering	24	Testing and piloting SKG-IF and FAIR-IF	32	Production system
Month	Description								
18	Users, DMP and FAIR tools requirement gathering								
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32	Production system								

4.3. International Virtual Observatory Alliance Registry (IVOA Registry)

Name	IVOA Registry		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	http://rofr.ivoa.net/ https://registry.euro-vo.org/evor/#home (GUI) http://dc.g-vo.org/browse/rr/q (RegTAP protocol) http://voparis-rr.obspm.fr/browse/rr/q (RegTAP protocol)		
Version	N/A	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	IVOA	Contributors	All data providers (many, worldwide)
License	Not specified		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint using IVOA RegTAP protocol		
Code repository URL	Several implementations, relying on several frameworks.		
Documentation URL	For data providers: https://wiki.ivoa.net/twiki/bin/view/IVOA/GettingIntoTheRegistry For users: https://wiki.ivoa.net/twiki/bin/view/IVOA/IvoaResReg#How%20do%20I%20use%20it?		

Other repositories	N/A								
PID	No PID for software.								
Software Quality Assurance measures	Each framework has its own implementation. However, the interfaces must pass validation tests (see IVOA Validator tools)								
Work performed	Preparing the connection to the SKG IF, as an extra access method to the IVOA registry. Proposing "DataAccessService" object in SKG-IF.								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Design of the SKG-IF Interface</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>First prototype of the SKG-IF</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>SKG-IF interface on IVOA Registry at ObsParis</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Design of the SKG-IF Interface	24	First prototype of the SKG-IF	32	SKG-IF interface on IVOA Registry at ObsParis
Month	Description								
18	Design of the SKG-IF Interface								
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32	SKG-IF interface on IVOA Registry at ObsParis								

4.4. Joint European Research Infrastructure of Coastal Observatories - Coastal Ocean Resource Environment (JERICO-CORE)

Name	JERICO Coastal Ocean Resource Environment (JERICO-CORE)		
Category	SKG / Supporting Service and Platform		
Service URL	https://ui.core.jerico-ri.eu and https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu (deprovisioned at end of JERICO-S3 project) https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/jerico_core/home (Blue Cloud VRE will host OSTrails interoperable SKG/DMP/FAIR assessment services)		
Version	0.2.9	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	JERICO	Contributors	IEEE, SOCIB, MARIS, IFREMER, AZTI, ETT, BLIT, IODE, CNRS-LOV, CNR, FMI,

			TALTECH, SYKE, EPOS, RBINS, SMHI				
License	All Rights Reserved						
Forms of availability	Gitlab repository, docker container registry.						
Code repository URL	SDK https://gitlab.priv.socib.es/data-center/ejerico_harvester API https://giltab.priv.socib.es/jerico/core_endpoint https://gitlab.priv.socib.es/jerico/core_endpoint/container_registry						
Documentation URL	https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/swagger (deprovisioned at end of JERICO-S3 project)						
Other repositories	https://github.com/socib/jerico-core.metadata https://pypi.org/project/ejerico-harvester						
PID	Not available						
Software Quality Assurance measures	Static code analysis, accessibility compliance testing.						
Work performed	<p>The work performed to date addresses the following requirements: DMP-R1, DMP-R3, SKG.R3, IF-R1, IF-R3, IF-R5. They are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data model evaluation and re-design to comply with RDA standards - Storage re-design to facilitate assessments - Integration of DMP in SKG - DMP editor - Harvesters' agent integration into DMP editor <p>Developments of JERCO-SKG and SOCIB SKG are being aligned.</p>						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	18	
Month	Description						
18							

	24	
	32	Deploy the tools in the JERICO Virtual Research Environment

4.5. OpenAIRE Graph

Name	OpenAIRE Graph		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://graph.openaire.eu/		
Version	10.0.1 ⁹	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE	Contributors	OpenAIRE, ARC, CNR, University of Athens, University of Minho, University of Bielefeld, University of Warsaw, National Documentation Centre (EKT), Greece ¹⁰¹¹
License	CC-BY Overview OpenAIRE Graph Documentation - https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint, data dumps, APIs		
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/openaire-graph-docs		
Documentation URL	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/ Overview OpenAIRE Graph Documentation		

⁹ OpenAIRE Graph Changelog:

https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/changelog?utm_source=chatgpt.com

¹⁰ OpenAIRE Graph - The Team: <https://graph.openaire.eu/team>

¹¹ The OpenAIRE Research Graph Data Model:

https://zenodo.org/records/2643199?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Other repositories	Zenodo for data dumps								
PID	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7488618								
Software Quality Assurance measures	Regular updates, community feedback integration, adherence to open standards								
Work performed	The OpenAIRE Graph data model has been mapped onto the first version of the SKG-IF guidelines with the aim of creating a workflow for generating a dump of the Graph compatible with the SKG-IF.								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>SKG-IF data dump publicly available and ALFA release of AKG-IF APIs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>BETA release of SKG-IF APIs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>PROD release of SKG-IF APIs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	SKG-IF data dump publicly available and ALFA release of AKG-IF APIs	24	BETA release of SKG-IF APIs	32	PROD release of SKG-IF APIs
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18	SKG-IF data dump publicly available and ALFA release of AKG-IF APIs								
24	BETA release of SKG-IF APIs								
32	PROD release of SKG-IF APIs								

4.6. European Synchrotron Radiation Facility Data Portal (ESRF-DP)

Name	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility Data Portal		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://data.esrf.fr		
Version	n/a	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility	Contributors	none
License	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MIT License 		
Forms of availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web site: https://data.esrf.fr API service: https://icatplus.esrf.fr/ 		

Code repository URL	https://gitlab.esrf.fr/icat/data-portal								
Documentation URL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://icat.gitlab-pages.esrf.fr/data-portal/ • https://icat.gitlab-pages.esrf.fr/icat-plus/ • https://icatplus.esrf.fr/api-docs/#/ 								
Other repositories	https://gitlab.esrf.fr/icat/drac								
PID	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0e42aa								
Software Quality Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automated Testing: unit, integration, and end-to-end tests • CI/CD: use pipelines to run tests, build the application and deployment • Code reviews 								
Work performed	<p>ESRF Data Portal, stores metadata about datasets generated at ESRF facility. Metadata is also exported to Datacite when minting DOI for these datasets.</p> <p>Work performed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SKG-R4: In ESRF Data Portal code. improve dataset metadata sent to Datacite (grant, subject/topic, affiliations) 								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>SKG-R2 participation to RDA SKG-IF API Design</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>SKG-R1 Update of internal new metadata sources used by datasets and publications (focus on topic: PaNET technique ontology, and science domain) Implement SKG-IF API on PUMA (ESRF internal SKG) to expose dataset/publication relation and topics. Implement SKG-IF API on ESRF Data Portal to expose datasets</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>SKG-R4 In ESRF Data Portal. improve dataset metadata. add link to citing publication. (source used PUMA, internal SKG)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	SKG-R2 participation to RDA SKG-IF API Design	24	SKG-R1 Update of internal new metadata sources used by datasets and publications (focus on topic: PaNET technique ontology, and science domain) Implement SKG-IF API on PUMA (ESRF internal SKG) to expose dataset/publication relation and topics. Implement SKG-IF API on ESRF Data Portal to expose datasets	32	SKG-R4 In ESRF Data Portal. improve dataset metadata. add link to citing publication. (source used PUMA, internal SKG)
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32	SKG-R4 In ESRF Data Portal. improve dataset metadata. add link to citing publication. (source used PUMA, internal SKG)								

4.7. SOCIB KB

Name	SOCIB SKG		
Category	SKG/Supporting Service and Platform		
Service URL	https://search.ws.socib.es/api/ (internal) https://search.ws.socib.es (internal)		
Version	N/A	TRL	g ¹²
Copyright owner(s)	SOCIB	Contributors	SOCIB
License	Proprietary - All Rights Reserved		
Forms of availability	Gitlab repository (source code)		
Code repository URL	https://gitlab.priv.socib.es/data-center/socib_api_search		
Documentation URL	Not available		
Other repositories	Not available		
PID	Not available		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Static code analysis, accessibility compliance testing.		
Work performed	The work performed to date addresses the following requirements: DMP-R1, DMP-R3, SKG.R3, IF-R1, IF-R3, IF-R5. They are the following:		

¹² For specific internal use

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data model evaluation and re-design to comply with RDA standards • Storage re-design to facilitate assessments • Integration of DMP in SKG • DMP editor • Harvesters' agent integration into DMP editor <p>Developments of JERCO-SKG and SOCIB SKG are being aligned.</p>								
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Month	Description								
18	Define use cases and deploy the first instance of the DMP Editor								
24	Align the SOCIB tools (SKG, DMP, FAIR assessments) with OSTrails Commons								
32	Implementation of SKG-IF based API								

4.8. SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP)

Name	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace (SSHOMP)		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/		
Version	N/A	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	DARIAH/CLARIN/CES SDA	Contributors	DARIAH/CLARIN/CESSDA plus EB
License	Apache-2.0 license: https://github.com/SSHOC/sshoc-marketplace-frontend#Apache-2.0-1-ov-file		
Forms of availability	service endpoint: https://marketplace-api.sshopencloud.eu/swagger-ui/index.html?url=/v3/api-docs app-marketplace: https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/		

Code repository URL	https://github.com/SSHOC/sshoc-marketplace-frontend and https://github.com/SSHOC/sshoc-marketplace-backend								
Documentation URL	https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/about/implementation https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/contribute/metadata-guidelines								
Other repositories	Not available								
PID	Does not apply as the SSHOMP is a repository itself. For entries, PIDs are recorded if available but SSHOMP does not issue PIDs.								
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>We have implemented the following quality assurance measures to ensure the reliability and security of our codebase:</p> <p>Testing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit Tests: Ensuring individual components function as expected. Integration Tests: Verifying that different parts of the system work together seamlessly. Code Coverage: Metrics are available to illustrate the extent of test coverage <p>Security:</p> <p>While penetration testing and static code analysis have not yet been performed, we are open to collaborating with the security team to explore and execute these measures if needed.</p> <p>Code Quality:</p> <p>Current testing practices indirectly support code quality by identifying regressions and functional issues.</p>								
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provided tool analysis information in the context of WP2. • contributed SSHOMP perspective to “A Research Community Perspective for using SKGs for Modelling and Exchange of Research Metadata” 								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>First implementation of SKG-IF based API by MP, provide feedback and contributions.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Final version of SKG-based API, evaluated through use cases (Marketplace with new entities from other SKGs)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18		24	First implementation of SKG-IF based API by MP, provide feedback and contributions.	32	Final version of SKG-based API, evaluated through use cases (Marketplace with new entities from other SKGs)
Month	Description								
18									
24	First implementation of SKG-IF based API by MP, provide feedback and contributions.								
32	Final version of SKG-based API, evaluated through use cases (Marketplace with new entities from other SKGs)								

4.9. Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)

Name	Virtual Language Observatory		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://vlo.clarin.eu/		
Version	4.12.1	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	CLARIN ERIC	Contributors	CLARIN centers
License	GPL v3.0		
Forms of availability	Code repository , SSHOC open marketplace		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/clarin-eric/VLO		
Documentation URL	Users: https://vlo.clarin.eu/help Developers: https://github.com/clarin-eric/VLO/blob/master/README.md		
PID	https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.429b28		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Software analysis using Snyk: https://snyk.io/ Continuous Integration incl. automated tests. SauceLab for browser testing: https://saucelabs.com/		
Work performed	The basis for the SKG IF support by the VLO will be CMDI2RDF, which has been updated to deal with the latest version of CMDI, i.e., 1.2.		
Milestones	Month	Description	
	18	Update the mapping from CMDI to RDF to use RDF*, which should simplify some more problematic mappings, i.e., for attributes	
	24	Support for the SKG IF	
	32	Interaction with neighbouring SKG's	

4.10. OPUS CTA Provenance

Name	OPUS (Observatoire de Paris UWS System)		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	Test service at https://voparis-uws-test.obspm.fr/		
Version	V0.5	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	PADC (Paris Astronomical Data Centre)	Contributors	
License	MIT License		
Forms of availability	code repository / service endpoint		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/ParisAstronomicalDataCentre/OPUS		
Documentation URL	https://opus-job-manager.readthedocs.io https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2022ASPC..532..451S		
Other repositories			
PID	DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14833881		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Unit tests		
Work performed	<p>None in the context of OSTrails, but OPUS is a reference implementation for handling Provenance information for the processing of data products through. As such, it provides an interface to expose provenance graphs compatible with IVOA and W3C standards.</p> <p>We are thus preparing the connection to the SKG IF for the access to provenance information.</p>		

Milestones	Month	Description
	18	Design of the SKG-IF Interface
	24	First prototype of the SKG-IF
	32	SKG-IF interface integrated to OPUS

5. FAIR Assessment Platforms

5.1. CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV)

Name	CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV) - ID006		
Category	FAIR Assessment Platform		
Service URL	https://cmv.cessda.eu/#!validation		
Version	3.6.0	TRL	g ¹³
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0 Documentation and Profiles: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint, app marketplace		
Code repository URL	Application: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.core https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.server User Guide: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.documentation Metadata Profiles: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.metadata.profiles		
Documentation URL	User Guide: https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/index.html		

¹³ <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

	<p>API: https://api.tech.CESSDA.eu/ (select 'CESSDA Metadata Validator')</p>
<p>Other repositories</p>	<p>Zenodo:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5711086 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4680639 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681200 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4050123 <p>EOSC EU Node Marketplace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/software?q=CESSDA%20Metadata%20Validator
<p>PID</p>	<p>10.5281/zenodo.5711086</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.4680639</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.4681200</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.4050123</p>
<p>Software Quality Assurance measures</p>	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.CESSDA.eu/sml/index.html). Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/CESSDA/CESSDA.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md - https://github.com/CESSDA/CESSDA.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md <p>The Jenkins build breaks if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved: https://docs.tech.CESSDA.eu/software/quality-gate.html</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and README files badged accordingly. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/CESSDA/CESSDA.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md - https://github.com/CESSDA/CESSDA.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md <p>Tooling</p>

	<p>Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis)</p> <p>SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability)</p> <p>JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)</p>								
Work performed	None								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Define use cases.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Define use cases.	24	First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.	32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
Month	Description								
18	Define use cases.								
24	First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.								
32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.								

5.2. FAIR-Aware

Name	FAIR-Aware		
Category	FAIR Knowledge Assessment tool		
Service URL	https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl (English) https://dorum.fr/appli-fair-aware-pleine-page-vf/ (French)		
Version	1.0.1 (Current production version)	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	Version 1.0.1 ¹⁴ Version 2.0: KNAW-DANS	Contributors	
License	MIT License		

¹⁴ From the homepage of FAIR-Aware v.1.0.1 and GitHub repository - © Copyright 2021 - FAIRsFAIR “Fostering FAIR Data Practices In Europe”

Forms of availability	Code repository containing HTML, JavaScript and CSS plus images and documentation.									
Code repository URL	https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/fair-assessment-tool/tree/master									
Documentation URL	https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/fair-assessment-tool/tree/master/documents									
Other repositories	N/A									
PID	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5084664									
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Not known if quality assurance measures were applied at development time of version 1.0 and unfortunately the original coder has retired. However, it does not pass any badges of Software Quality Assurance as a Service (SQaaS) assessment, but does pass Code Accessibility, Licensing and Code metadata criteria.</p> <p>Version 1.0.1 does not meet web accessibility compliance WCAG 2.2, EEA and EN 301 549 - AccessibilityChecker.org</p>									
<i>Work performed</i>	<p>Guidance and glossary content extracted and converted into JSON files ready for import into any FAIR guidance system (e.g. Compliance Assessment Toolkit) (FAIR-R5)</p> <p>Further development of the specification for version 2.0 of FAIR-Aware undertaken to facilitate language independence, and the ability to create guidance and question sets for other digital object types. (IF-R2, IF-R4)</p>									
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>FAIR-Aware 2.0 and documentation completed and available in repository. V1 installation migrated to V2.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Additional digital object types added to assessment questions and guidance</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Month	Description	18	FAIR-Aware 2.0 and documentation completed and available in repository. V1 installation migrated to V2.	24	Additional digital object types added to assessment questions and guidance	32	
Month	Description									
18	FAIR-Aware 2.0 and documentation completed and available in repository. V1 installation migrated to V2.									
24	Additional digital object types added to assessment questions and guidance									
32										

5.3. FAIR Evaluator (renamed FAIR Champion)

Name	FAIR Champion		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	https://tools.ostrails.eu/champion/sets/		
Version	0.1	TRL	6/7 ¹⁵
Copyright owner(s)	Mark D. Wilkinson	Contributors	
License	MIT		
Forms of availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Container - Code repository - Service endpoint. 		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/markwilkinson/FAIR-Champion		
Documentation URL	TBD		
Other repositories	N/A		
PID	N/A		
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Creation of a test harness for Champion is in progress (the data models were still being modified until the delivery of D1.2). The Champion has two independent repositories- The Champion assessment platform, and the Champion (individual) Tests. A test harness for the individual tests (using RSpec) to ensure their compliance with the EOSC-recommended FAIR Signposting metadata harvesting is part of the Champion Tests repository and shows 100% pass.</p> <p>All platforms must be tested against the JSON Schema for FAIR Test Results to ensure that their outputs are harmonized. This is</p>		

¹⁵ TRL presented refers to current revision; previous FAIR Evaluator TRL is 9.

	<p>currently done semi-automatically, and as of this Deliverable, the Champion and FOOPS! Platforms are compliant.</p>								
<p>Work performed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Examination of the ecosystem of FAIR assessment tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Result: FAIR Reference Model – Deliverable D1.2 - Comparison of the output from each tool - Harmonization of an output data structure (part of FAIR Reference Model) - Re-code of the Evaluator to implement the new data model - Re-code of the back-end of the Evaluator to use a triplestore rather than MySQL - Re-branding of the Evaluator “FAIR Champion” - Initial testing of interoperability between FAIR Champion and FOOPS! shows that they both adhere to the FAIR Test Results specification, thus the output from both Platforms can be correctly integrated. 								
<p>Milestones</p>	<p>Future milestones are entirely dependent on the participation of the other Interoperability Frameworks in their declaration of their expectations (which will change over the course of the project, as all IFs become more mature), and the domain-specific expectations fed to us from the OSTrails Pilots. We have an open document where all participants can add their expectations and domain-specific tests as they become aware of the need. We respond in-kind.</p> <p>As such, we cannot predict precise numbers or types of milestone – we can only adapt on an ongoing basis as we get feedback from these other participants. New tests will be authored on-demand. The architecture of the Champion itself will be modified, if needed.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="472 1429 1393 1594"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Ongoing adaptation to project needs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Ongoing adaptation to project needs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Ongoing adaptation to project needs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Ongoing adaptation to project needs	24	Ongoing adaptation to project needs	32	Ongoing adaptation to project needs
Month	Description								
18	Ongoing adaptation to project needs								
24	Ongoing adaptation to project needs								
32	Ongoing adaptation to project needs								

5.4. FAIR Validator

Name	FAIR Validator		
Category	FAIR Assessment Service		
Service URL	https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.metadata_validator/overview		
Version	TBD	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE ¹⁶	Contributors	OpenAIRE
License	Apache-2.0: https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0		
Forms of availability	Code repository + Service endpoint + Web application accessible online.		
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/uoa-validator-engine2 https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/uoa-validator-api		
Documentation URL	TBD		
Other repositories	N/A		
PID	TBD		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Regular updates and maintenance by the OpenAIRE team to ensure compliance with evolving guidelines.		
Work performed	OpenAIRE has been working to adopt the FAIR-IF specification for the FAIR Metadata Validator. It is currently under development and not presentable yet. Once we incorporate the FAIR-IF specification		

¹⁶ OpenAIRE Service Catalogue:
https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.metadata_validator/overview

	model in the data model, we will proceed to the respective tests and metrics.	
Milestones		
	Month	Description
	18	Implementation of the tests and test-results specifications in alignment with the FAIR-IF reference model and ongoing adaptation to project needs.
	24	Implementation of the tests and test-results specifications in alignment with the FAIR-IF reference model and ongoing adaptation to project needs.
32	Perform tests and benchmarks to evaluate the integration into the Ostrails ecosystem.	

5.5. FAIR Research Objects Assessment (FAIROS)

Name	FAIROS		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	http://w3id.org/FAIROS/api		
Version	0.0.2	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	Esteban Gonzalez Daniel Garijo Alejandro Benitez	Contributors	Óscar Corcho
License	Apache 2.0 (https://github.com/oeg-upm/FAIR-Research-Object/blob/main/LICENSE)		
Forms of availability	Source code + Service endpoint		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/oeg-upm/FAIR-Research-Object		

Documentation URL	https://w3id.org/FAIROS								
Other repositories	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599423								
PID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599423								
Software Quality Assurance measures	Implementation of a test to assess the results and the availability of the service. In addition, we have done an integration test with ROHub. Example: https://www.rohub.org/998dccd6-7192-4d88-af39-6018c71e6bdf								
Work performed	The developers of FAIROs have been working in the FAIR-IF specification. Once the specifications are stable, we will modify tests and metrics accordingly.								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Adoption of the test specifications in accordance with the model defined in the FAIR-IF.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Adoption of the test result specifications in accordance with the model defined in the FAIR-IF.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Tests performed to evaluate the integration of the tool into the OSTrails ecosystem. The results of the tests should be published in the SKG.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Adoption of the test specifications in accordance with the model defined in the FAIR-IF.	24	Adoption of the test result specifications in accordance with the model defined in the FAIR-IF.	32	Tests performed to evaluate the integration of the tool into the OSTrails ecosystem. The results of the tests should be published in the SKG.
Month	Description								
18	Adoption of the test specifications in accordance with the model defined in the FAIR-IF.								
24	Adoption of the test result specifications in accordance with the model defined in the FAIR-IF.								
32	Tests performed to evaluate the integration of the tool into the OSTrails ecosystem. The results of the tests should be published in the SKG.								

5.6. Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS!)

Name	Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS!)		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	https://w3id.org/foops		
Version	0.2.0	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	Daniel Garijo, María Poveda	Contributors	Oscar Corcho

License	Apache 2.0 (https://github.com/oeg-upm/fair_ontologies/blob/main/LICENSE)									
Forms of availability	Code repository + Service endpoint									
Code repository URL	https://github.com/oeg-upm/fair_ontologies/									
Documentation URL	https://github.com/oeg-upm/fair_ontologies/blob/main/README.md									
Other repositories	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14768000 Catalogue of tests and metrics: https://w3id.org/foops/catalogue									
PID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14768000									
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Reference implementation of the FAIR-IF.</p> <p>Test definitions and metrics have passed a SHACL shape validation test to comply with the FAIR-IF test specification.</p> <p>FOOPS! Has a battery of tests to assess its performance when new issues are fixed.</p>									
Work performed	<p>This tool presents a reference implementation of the FAIR-IF, including tests, metrics and benchmarks.</p> <p>FAIR assessment tool for semantic artefacts, including RDF ontologies and vocabularies. Given an ontology URI, FOOPS! Will run a battery of tests to check its compliance with the FAIR principles and return suggestions on the key aspects to improve.</p> <p>We have adapted the test specification of FOOPS! To comply with the FAIR-IF specification, making it a reference implementation.</p>									
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Individual tests return data according to FAIR-IF</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Benchmarks are implemented in the tool</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Other services are able to invoke assessment with a full provenance trace, suggestions and rationale</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Month	Description	18	Individual tests return data according to FAIR-IF	24	Benchmarks are implemented in the tool	32	Other services are able to invoke assessment with a full provenance trace, suggestions and rationale
Month	Description									
18	Individual tests return data according to FAIR-IF									
24	Benchmarks are implemented in the tool									
32	Other services are able to invoke assessment with a full provenance trace, suggestions and rationale									

5.7. IVOA Services Validation

Name	IVOA service Validation		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	https://voparis-validation-reports.obspm.fr/api/		
Version	1.10	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	ObsParis	Contributors	CNRS
License	TBD.		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint		
Code repository URL	N/A		
Documentation URL	https://voparis-validation-reports.obspm.fr/		
Other repositories	N/A		
PID	N/A		
Software Quality Assurance measures	TBD		
Work performed	Preparing FAIR-Assessment metrics including IVOA service validation.		
Milestones	Month	Description	
	18	First draft of tests and metrics	
	24	First prototype	
	32	Effective assessment of ESCAPE Pilot resources	

5.8. PADC Validator

Name	PADC Validator Service		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	http://voparis-validator.obspm.fr/		
Version	TBD	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	ObsParis	Contributors	CNRS
License	TBD		
Forms of availability	service endpoint		
Code repository URL	TBD		
Documentation URL	TBD		
Other repositories	N/A		
PID	TBD		
Software Quality Assurance measures	TBD		
Work performed	Preparing FAIR-Assessment metrics including PADC Validator results		
Milestones	Month	Description	
	18	First draft of tests and metrics	
	24	First prototype	
	32	Effective assessment of ESCAPE Pilot resources	

6. Other Supporting Services and Platforms

6.1. CESSDA ELSST

Name	CESSDA European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) - ID003		
Category	Supporting Services and Platforms		
Service URL	https://thesauri.cessda.eu/elsst-5/en/		
Version	5.0	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC (content, not code)	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint, app marketplace		
Code repository URL	N/A (uses 3 rd party application to publish curated content)		
Documentation URL	User Guide: https://elsst.cessda.eu/ API: https://api.tech.cessda.eu/ (select 'CESSDA ELSST Thesaurus')		
Other repositories	Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4063933 EOSC EU Node Marketplace: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/data/50%257Cdoi_dedup_%253A%253Aa5095d6e7764ec39d2d9f5b448611c52 SSH Open Marketplace: https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/fljrOK		

PID	10.5281/zenodo.4063933									
Software Quality Assurance measures	N/A									
Work performed	None									
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Define Use Cases.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Month	Description	18	Define Use Cases.	24	First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.	32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
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32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.									

6.2. CESSDA Vocabulary Service

Name	CESSDA Vocabulary Service (CVS) - ID008		
Category	Supporting Services and Platforms		
Service URL	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/		
Version	3.3.1	TRL	8 ¹⁷
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0 Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint, app marketplace		

¹⁷ <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

Code repository URL	<p>Application: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cvs.two</p> <p>User Guide: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cvs.userguide</p> <p>Content Editors' Guide: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cvs.contentguide</p>
Documentation URL	<p>User Guide: https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/documentation/</p> <p>Content Editors' Guide: Only available to authenticated users</p> <p>API: https://api.tech.cessda.eu/ (select 'CESSDA Vocabulary Service')</p>
Other repositories	<p>Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6092398</p> <p>EOSC EU Node Marketplace: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/software/50%257Cdoi_dedup_%253A%253A394aacec99e0d7fb2ec782930d4cc739</p>
PID	10.5281/zenodo.6092398
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/sml/index.html)</p> <p>Examples: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md</p> <p>https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md</p> <p>The Jenkins build breaks if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved: https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/software/quality-gate.html</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and README files badged accordingly. Examples:</p> <p>https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md</p> <p>https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md</p>

Tooling	<p>Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis)</p> <p>SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability)</p> <p>JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)</p>										
Work Performed	None										
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Month</th> <th style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Define Use Cases.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	18	Define Use Cases.	24	First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.	32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
Month	Description										
18	Define Use Cases.										
24	First implementation of SKG-IF based API, provide feedback and contributions.										
32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.										

6.3. CESSDA Metadata Aggregator

Name	CESSDA Metadata Aggregator - ID048		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai		
Version	0.10.0	TRL	8 ¹⁸
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	<p>Software: EUPL-1.2</p> <p>Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/</p>		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint		

¹⁸ See: <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

Code repository URL	<p>OAI-PMH endpoint (SKG API):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.doc-store.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.client.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.oai-pmh-repo-handler.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.oai-pmh-repo-handler.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.devguide.git
Documentation URL	<p>OAI-PMH API: https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=Identify</p> <p>OAI-PMH Developer's guide: https://cessda-metadata-aggregator.readthedocs.io/en/stable/</p>
Other repositories	<p>Zenodo (OAI-PMH endpoint):</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779957</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779936</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779782</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779897</p>
PID	<p>OAI-PMH endpoint:</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.5779957</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.5779936</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.5779782</p> <p>10.5281/zenodo.5779897</p>
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/sml/index.html). Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md <p>The Jenkins build breaks if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/software/quality-gate.html)</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaas.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and README files badged accordingly. Examples:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md <p>Tooling</p> <p>Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis)</p> <p>SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability)</p> <p>JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)</p>								
Work performed	None.								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Incorporate more persistent identifiers such as ORCID and ROR.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>First implementation of SKG-IF compliant API.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Incorporate more persistent identifiers such as ORCID and ROR.	24	First implementation of SKG-IF compliant API.	32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
Month	Description								
18	Incorporate more persistent identifiers such as ORCID and ROR.								
24	First implementation of SKG-IF compliant API.								
32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.								

6.4. Lenticular Lens

Name	Lenticular Lens		
Category	Supporting Service		
Service URL	https://lenticularlens.org/		
Version	1.18	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	KNAW HuC	Contributors	KNAW HuC
License	MIT		
Forms of availability	code repository https://lenticularlens.goldenagents.org		

Code repository URL	https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens								
Documentation URL	https://lenticularlens.org/								
Other repositories	https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens-org https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens-gui-react https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens-postgresql								
PID	hdl:1148d8d1-a16d-4cf9-a5b9-07dedc027502								
Software Quality Assurance measures	Software analysis using Snyk: https://snyk.io/								
Work performed	LL must support the SKG IF, however the SKG IF specification is currently only partially finished: the model in dec. 2024 and the API is still to be specified.								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Support loading the data from any triple store</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Support the SKG-IF</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Support alignment of entities between OST SKGs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Support loading the data from any triple store	24	Support the SKG-IF	32	Support alignment of entities between OST SKGs
Month	Description								
18	Support loading the data from any triple store								
24	Support the SKG-IF								
32	Support alignment of entities between OST SKGs								

6.5. OpenAIRE Broker

Name	OpenAIRE Broker		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.broker/overview		
Version	OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard integration v3.3.1 Public API v3.4.3	TRL	9

Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE	Contributors	OpenAIRE, CNR
License	Software: GPL-3.0-or-later https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html		
Forms of availability	Accessible via the OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard and through APIs.		
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-applications/src/branch/master/apps/dhp-broker-application https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/main/dhp-workflows/dhp-broker-events https://github.com/openaire/broker-cmdline-client ¹⁹		
Documentation URL	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/apis/broker-api/		
Other repositories	https://central.sonatype.com/artifact/eu.openaire/broker-client		
PID	N/A		
Software Quality Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CI/CD infrastructure to ensure repeatable, trusted delivery. - Static Code Analysis using SonarQube software. - Unit tests 		
Work performed	<p>The work completed in the first period, up to month 14 (M14), focused on evaluating use cases to identify: (1) the types of digital objects involved, and (2) the relevant scientific publishing events. This analysis will inform the design of new subscription topics. The candidate topics are listed below, and the added value analysis will be completed within M18</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links between publications and peer reviews • Links between datasets and DMPs • Links between publications and datasets 		

¹⁹ 026_OpenAIRE-Broker.pptx:

https://openaireeu.sharepoint.com/:p:/s/OSTrails/EYvRDnO_CMIAgporO0LXNq0BqE2BRC8sVztXkCdq_2RzgA?e=Gyrhna

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata quality indicators based on the OpenAIRE Guidelines 								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Finalisation of the OpenAIRE Broker use cases for new subscription topics</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Pilot implementation</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Production release</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Finalisation of the OpenAIRE Broker use cases for new subscription topics	24	Pilot implementation	32	Production release
Month	Description								
18	Finalisation of the OpenAIRE Broker use cases for new subscription topics								
24	Pilot implementation								
32	Production release								

6.6. OpenOrgs

Name	OpenOrgs		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	Service: https://orgs.openaire.eu Portal: https://openorgs.openaire.eu		
Version	3.5.3	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE	Contributors	OpenAIRE, CNR, RBI
License	Software: GPL-3.0-or-later https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html		
Forms of availability	Via the public portal - https://openorgs.openaire.eu Via the data curation tool - https://openorgs.openaire.eu Via the OpenAIRE Graph API - https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/apis/graph-api/ Via the data snapshot - https://zenodo.org/records/13271358		
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-applications/src/branch/master/apps/dnet-orgs-database-application		
Documentation URL	https://openorgs.openaire.eu/what-is-openorgs https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/entities/organization		

Other repositories	https://maven.d4science.org/nexus/service/local/repositories/dnet45-snapshots/content/eu/dnetlib/dhp/dnet-orgs-database-application/maven-metadata.xml								
PID	N/A								
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Regular updates and the integration of community feedback to ensure reliability and continuous improvement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CI/CD infrastructure to ensure repeatable, trusted delivery. - Static Code Analysis using SonarQube software. - Unit tests 								
Work performed	<p>The work carried out until month 14 (M14) addressed two main tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The development of the OpenAIRE Graph API to return organization records. These records are built out of the curated information from the OpenOrgs database and includes organization persistent identifiers (ROR, PIC, ISNI, Wikidata, etc), alternative names, etc. Further developments will introduce a response format that conforms the SKG-IF specification. • To improve the synchronisation with other organisation DBs we begun a pilot activity with Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (vu.nl) focused on retrieving complete and authoritative information about Dutch organization (sub)units from CRIS systems. Integrating this data, after curation via OpenOrgs and in conjunction with affiliation data, will enhance the accuracy and coverage of the Netherlands monitor. Furthermore, this approach can serve as a model for similar initiatives in other countries where comparable information is accessible. 								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="448 1565 651 1610">Month</th> <th data-bbox="651 1565 1374 1610">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1610 651 1688">18</td> <td data-bbox="651 1610 1374 1688">Finalisation of the 1st API release and evaluation of the list of CRIS Systems to onboard in the pilot</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1688 651 1890">24</td> <td data-bbox="651 1688 1374 1890">Draft of the extension of the API response format aligned with the SKG-IF specifications and preliminary evaluation of the Dutch organisation subunits curation results in the OpenOrgs platform</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1890 651 1968">32</td> <td data-bbox="651 1890 1374 1968">Production release of the SKG-IF compliant Graph API response format.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Finalisation of the 1 st API release and evaluation of the list of CRIS Systems to onboard in the pilot	24	Draft of the extension of the API response format aligned with the SKG-IF specifications and preliminary evaluation of the Dutch organisation subunits curation results in the OpenOrgs platform	32	Production release of the SKG-IF compliant Graph API response format.
Month	Description								
18	Finalisation of the 1 st API release and evaluation of the list of CRIS Systems to onboard in the pilot								
24	Draft of the extension of the API response format aligned with the SKG-IF specifications and preliminary evaluation of the Dutch organisation subunits curation results in the OpenOrgs platform								
32	Production release of the SKG-IF compliant Graph API response format.								

6.7. ROHub

Name	ROHub		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://www.rohub.org/		
Version	Portal v.4.0.2 Service v2.0.359	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	PSNC	Contributors	
License	ROHub portal and service: Closed ROHub Python library MIT		
Forms of availability	ROHub portal available via portal endpoint, possible also binary for on-site deployments ROHub service available via service endpoint, possible also binary for on-site deployments Python library in code repository, pip package		
Code repository URL	Service: https://gitlab.pcss.pl/rohub/rohub-backend/rohub2020 (private) Portal: https://gitlab.pcss.pl/rohub/rohub-frontend/rohub2020-frontend (private) Python library: https://gitlab.pcss.pl/daisd-public/rohub/rohub-api (public)		
Documentation URL	https://reliance-eosc.github.io/rohub-portal-documentation/ Tutorial: https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/tutorials.html API: https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/modules.html API Jupyter Notebook demo: https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/sample-notebooks		

Other repositories	N/A	
PID	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.d3c5fd https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013832	
Software Quality Assurance measures	Unit testing, integrated unit testing, continuous integration, sentry, nagios	
Work performed	<p>Improved existing connections of ROHub with other OSTrails tools, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAIROs for the FAIR assessment of RO-Crate research objects. • OpenAire SKG to publish RO-Crates, Jupyter notebooks and data cubes resources, • Argos to enable the generation of RO-Crate research objects from DMPs, to enable management of MA-DMP. For this also some improvements were made in the Argos extension by PSNC to export DMPs directly to ROHub. <p>ROHub exposes OpenAPI specifications and REST architectural styles (IF-R8), and the representation and exchange of data in semantically rich formats like RDF to enhance interoperability (IF-R10), particularly using RO-crate specification for data exchange (IF-R1), which is based on JSON-LD data format (IF-R3), the use of PIDs for referencing data and contextual entities (IF-R5), and on using common published vocabularies, chiefly schema.org (IF-R7). Additionally, initial discussion with other partners of polish pilot have taken place to facilitate integration of institutional repositories of research data and publications (IF-R11)</p>	
Milestones	Month	Description
	18	Full sync with latest developments in FAIROs, OpenAire SKG and Argos
	24	Implementation of initial version of OSTrails IFs, particularly the SKG IF to expose ROHub data as SKG, and initial works towards integration with FAIROs via FAIR-IF and Argos via DMP-IF, initial integration with institutional repositories
	32	Implementation and use of OSTrails IF for communication with FAIROs (if compliant),

	OpenAire SKG (if compliant) and Argos (if compliant)
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6.8. SOMEF

Name	Software Metadata Extraction Framework (SoMEF)		
Category	Supporting Service		
Service URL	https://somef.linkeddata.es/#/		
Version	0.9.7_2	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	Daniel Garijo	Contributors	
License	MIT License (https://github.com/KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery/somef/blob/master/LICENSE)		
Forms of availability	Container + Source code		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery/somef/		
Documentation URL	https://somef.readthedocs.io/en/latest/		
Other repositories	N/A		
PID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14780377 https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:118b192ae433383ff1f60512d3869b24b0648393;origin=https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3477929;visit=swh:1:snp:64a22f7c09abdf2b834d6bcbe1f852ceab9da699;anchor=swh:1:rel:0ae2f5e55132f9a3bb6aedc1a74c1fc603e78474;path=KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery-somef-a33c984		

Software Quality Assurance measures	Battery of tests implemented, GitHub actions for releases, Poetry for reproducibility								
Work performed	N/A (this tool is used inside FAIROs)								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>The tool will be adapted to recognize metadata that is important for FAIRness</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18		24		32	The tool will be adapted to recognize metadata that is important for FAIRness
Month	Description								
18									
24									
32	The tool will be adapted to recognize metadata that is important for FAIRness								

6.9. SSH Data Citation Service

Name	SSH Data Citation Service (DCS)		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html		
Version	O.5	TRL	4
Copyright owner(s)	Institute of Information Science and Technologies "Alessandro Faedo" - (ISTI) - CNR	Contributors	ISTI – CNR, ILC - CNR
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0		
Forms of availability	Source code available, public REST API, demo Web UI		
Code repository URL	https://gitea-s2i2s.isti.cnr.it/concordia/sshoc-citationservice		

Documentation URL	<p>Technical documentation is being created, Swagger documentation for REST API is available here:</p> <p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citationservice/swagger-ui.html</p> <p>A document describing motivations and design assumptions of the DCS:</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/3595965</p> <p>A scientific paper describing the DCS:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-16802-4_32</p>								
Other repositories	N/A								
PID	N/A								
Software Quality Assurance measures	The development environment is being created, it will include state of art frameworks to implement code analysis and testing								
Work performed	DCS will use the SKG IF, therefore work is in progress to update APIs to act as integration layer implementing the SKG IF model (as for dec. 2024 yet to be finalised). Activity is being carried on improving the Authentication Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) module of the DCS to implement OAuth 2.0, which is one of the possible protocols implemented in OSTrails (see IF-R4)								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="466 1359 667 1406">Month</th> <th data-bbox="667 1359 1393 1406">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="466 1406 667 1525">18</td> <td data-bbox="667 1406 1393 1525">Development environment defined; Authentication and Authorization interoperability with SKG IF implemented</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="466 1525 667 1608">24</td> <td data-bbox="667 1525 1393 1608">Alignment of API with SKG implemented, TRL improved to level 8</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="466 1608 667 1644">32</td> <td data-bbox="667 1608 1393 1644">Tests completed; DCS released</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Development environment defined; Authentication and Authorization interoperability with SKG IF implemented	24	Alignment of API with SKG implemented, TRL improved to level 8	32	Tests completed; DCS released
Month	Description								
18	Development environment defined; Authentication and Authorization interoperability with SKG IF implemented								
24	Alignment of API with SKG implemented, TRL improved to level 8								
32	Tests completed; DCS released								

6.10. SSH Vocabulary Commons

Name	Social Sciences & Humanities Vocabulary Commons		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse		
Version	N/A (currently based on Skosmos 2.16)	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	N/A	Contributors	ACDH-CH (ÖAW), CLARIN, SSHOC
License	MIT for the underlying software (Skosmos): https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-update-theme/blob/main/LICENSE		
Forms of availability	Code repository: https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-common Vocabulary dumps: https://github.com/SSHOC/vocabularies Container: https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-common/pkgs/container/vocabs-common API endpoint: https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/rest/v1/		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-common		
Documentation URL	https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/en/about For underlying software (Skosmos): https://github.com/NatLibFi/Skosmos/wiki For API (Skosmos): http://api.finto.fi/doc/#/		
Other repositories	Not available		
PID	N/A		

Software Quality Assurance measures	Responsibility of the developers of the Skosmos software (National Library Finland).								
Work performed	<p>Preparatory activities: Investigating & discussing additional functionality improving FAIRness.</p> <p>Sharing editorial responsibility for the content. ao. for merged metadata vocabularies which should lead to better interoperability and discovery potential.</p>								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td> <p>Study and planning reports for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitating shared editorial responsibility - Expanding federated vocabulary (metadata) search - Role of vocabulary services in relation to SKGs <p>Exploring relation of Vocabulary Service to FAIRsharing</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Publications and potential implementation</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18		24	<p>Study and planning reports for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitating shared editorial responsibility - Expanding federated vocabulary (metadata) search - Role of vocabulary services in relation to SKGs <p>Exploring relation of Vocabulary Service to FAIRsharing</p>	32	Publications and potential implementation
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32	Publications and potential implementation								

6.11. DataRepositóriUM

Name	DataRepositóriUM		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/		
Version	Dataverse 4.20	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	<p>DataRepositóriUM: University of Minho</p> <p>Dataverse software: Institute for Quantitative Social Science, Harvard University</p>	Contributors	<p>Dataverse software: Global Dataverse Community Consortium</p>

License	The Dataverse software is licensed under the Apache License Version 2.0. https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse/blob/develop/LICENSE.md
Forms of availability	Via the public portal: https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/ Via the repository OAI-PMH interface: https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/oai?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_dc Via the API (Dataverse): https://guides.dataverse.org/en/4.20/api/intro.html#lists-of-dataverse-apis
Code repository URL	https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse
Documentation URL	https://guides.dataverse.org/en/4.20/developers/index.html https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/admin/index.html
Other repositories	Docker Container Guide: https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/container/index.html Dataverse roadmap: https://www.iq.harvard.edu/roadmap-dataverse-project
PID	N/A
Software Quality Assurance measures	Quality Assurance measures described at https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/qa/overview.html
Work performed	Tool analysis to evaluate the compliance with OSTrails Interoperability Framework. The following topics represents some of the requirements that are being addressed: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Digital objects deposited in repository assigned with PIDs (DOI);- DataRepositoriUM is compatible with the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives (https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html) and its metadata is being aggregated by OpenAIRE (https://explore.openaire.eu/search/dataprovider?pid=r3d100013173);- DataRepositoriUM supports several metadata export formats (Dublin Core, DDI, DataCite, JSON (native Dataverse Software format), OAI_ORE, OpenAIRE, Schema.org JSON-LD).

	<p>- DataRepositoriUM supports the OAI-PMH protocol for metadata harvesting, which interface is https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/oai</p> <p>- Native API https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/api/native-api.html.</p> <p>Further work will be carried out to align with the OSTrails IF, so the tool can be integrated to benefit from the OSTrails software to be developed, mainly the FAIR assessment of digital objects.</p>								
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>Initial integration of the FAIR assessment tool</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>Implementation of the FAIR assessment tool</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Full Implementation of the FAIR assessment tool and assess digital objects in line with the Portuguese National Pilot.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18	Initial integration of the FAIR assessment tool	24	Implementation of the FAIR assessment tool	32	Full Implementation of the FAIR assessment tool and assess digital objects in line with the Portuguese National Pilot.
Month	Description								
18	Initial integration of the FAIR assessment tool								
24	Implementation of the FAIR assessment tool								
32	Full Implementation of the FAIR assessment tool and assess digital objects in line with the Portuguese National Pilot.								

6.12. TUWRD

Name	TU Wien Research Data		
Category	Supporting Service and Platform		
Service URL	https://researchdata.tuwien.ac.at		
Version	Version 12	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	CERN and Invenio Community	Contributors	TU Wien and TU Graz
License	MIT (URL: https://opensource.org/license/mit)		
Forms of availability	code repository: https://github.com/inveniosoftware/awesome-invenio service endpoint: https://researchdata.tuwien.ac.at		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/inveniosoftware		
Documentation URL	https://inveniordm.docs.cern.ch		

Other repositories	https://gitlab.tuwien.ac.at/crdm										
PID	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.88d503										
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Different measures for the various packages, but all of them use test suites.</p> <p>Custom TU Wien packages have static code analysis via SonarQube and use code linters.</p> <p>TU Wien Research Data as a service was also subjected to two penetration tests</p>										
Work performed	None presently										
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Connect to DAMAP using DMP-IF</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	18		24		32	Connect to DAMAP using DMP-IF
Month	Description										
18											
24											
32	Connect to DAMAP using DMP-IF										

6.13. RCAAP

Name	RCAAP Portuguese Open Access Scientific Repositories		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://www.rcaap.pt/		
Version	n/a	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	FCT-FCCN (front-end); La referencia (back-end)	Contributors	University of Minho
License	Front-end NA; Back-end AJPL3.0		
Forms of availability	Via the public portal: https://www.rcaap.pt/		

	<p>Via the repository OAI-PMH interface: https://www.rcaap.pt/oai/opeaire4?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_o_opeaire</p>								
Code repository URL	https://github.com/lareferencia/lareferencia-lrharvester-app								
Documentation URL	https://projeto.rcaap.pt/								
Other repositories	https://www.rcaap.pt/directory.jsp https://www.indexar.pt								
PID	NA								
Software Quality Assurance measures	NA								
Work performed	None								
Milestones	<p><i>None set presently. To be placed in next period of the project.</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18		24		32	
Month	Description								
18									
24									
32									

7. Conclusions – Next Steps

This report shows that at least a very large subset of tools identified in D2.1 have evolved in the context of OSTrails WP2 in the directions set by its vision, fulfilling the requirements identified, the directions diffused inside the project from other, concurrently running tasks of WP1, WP3 and WP4, during the period of the project that has elapsed.

A brief analysis of the results is that:

- The majority of the software is Open Source under common FOSS licenses, and many of the services presented are easily accessible.
- At least 33 platforms have an active evolution plan in the context of OSTrails, with specific expectations and targets.
- Out of those, approximately 75% of the tools have already evolved in this first release.

Figure 1: Tools implementing refinements in OSTrails WP2, per category

Figure 2: Tools reporting refinements to date in D2.2

- Several tools have not yet made any amendments to their software to date but will nevertheless aim to implement refinements to align with the OSTrails requirements and specifications during the remainder of the project. This typically includes tasks such as:
 - Define Use Cases and finalise interoperability specifications in terms of APIs.
 - Create a first implementation of the data models, APIs (e.g. SKG-IF based API) or functionalities needed and provide feedback and contributions.
 - Test the use cases against the newly built features, capabilities or larger scale outcomes (e.g. SKG federation).

Several tools have released interim versions or iterations prior to this general release, for example with the aim to validate integration as early as possible or to provide early support for pilots. This trend is expected to continue in addition to the two more official releases, to be reported as Deliverables D2.3 and D2.4.

8. References

1. Suchánek, M., Martínková, J., Wilkinson, M., Garijo, D., Miksa, T., Manghi, P., Dyume, R., Rey Mazón, M., Moilanen, K., Heinonen, M., Broeder, D., Spichtinger, D., Windhouwer, M., Príncipe, P., Vodopijevec, A., Macan, B., Steinhoff, W., Priddy, M., & Kontopidi, M. (2024). D2.1: Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880235>

Annex I – Description Template

The following template has been utilised in order to achieve a homogenously presentation of the work and outcomes for each platform.

Software/Service XYX

Name	Present the formal name of the service, platform, tool		
Category	<i>Choose one of: DMP/SKG/FAIR Assessment/Supporting Service or Platform</i>		
Service URL	<i>Place service URL, if applicable</i>		
Version	<i>If a versioning number is present and relevant, it should be placed here</i>	TRL	<i>Present the TRL of the item as of this release</i>
Copyright owner(s)	<i>Name the copyright owners (no need for details)</i>	Contributors	<i>If more contributors exist besides the copyright owners present those here.</i>
License	<i>Present the license name and its URL for reference.</i>		
Forms of availability	<i>Pick any or multiple of: Binary / container / code repository / source code bundle / service endpoint / app-marketplace ... (if various elements are provided in different forms, clarify which element is provided in each form).</i>		
Code repository URL	<i>Place repository URL (GitHub etc.). If FOSS, the repo should be accessible. If private, the link may be skipped, however still some evidence should be here for reference.</i>		
Documentation URL	<i>Present a (public) documentation URL</i>		
Other repositories	<i>Point out any other repositories related to software access in its various forms (e.g. docker hub, maven, Zenodo, community repositories etc.) along with URLs of the software.</i>		
PID	<i>PID for the software (good practice to have one, however if not available save for next iteration of the deliverable).</i>		

<p>Software Quality Assurance measures</p>	<p><i>Enumerate briefly the quality assurance measures taken. Security, code quality, testing measures should be presented. For instance: Static code analysis, penetration testing, accessibility compliance testing etc. If details for the processes are needed place those in the document below this card.</i></p>								
<p>Work performed</p>	<p><i>Present briefly the work performed up to M14. This is the most essential part of this document. Present here only work that is performed in OSTrails and in alignment with its objectives!</i></p> <p><i>Identify which of the requirements or directives presented Chapter 2 are being addressed during this period.</i></p> <p><i>Explicitly present work towards the alignment to draft architectural interoperability directives of OSTrails as known up to M12.</i></p>								
<p>Milestones</p>	<p><i>Enumerate major milestones of your future work in OSTrails referring to project months estimation ensuring alignment with the two updates of D2.2 at M24 and M32. (interim milestones may be present for some software depending on pilots and other dependencies, so add those at will). Adding an MTR milestone (M18) can also be helpful.</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="472 1048 1391 1216"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18		24		32	
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